

Dry mechanochemical route to nanocomposites containing multi-layer graphene

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to investigate the feasibility of preparing an electrically conductive nanocomposite containing graphite or graphene from glucose mechanochemically intercalated into montmorillonite (MMT). Four different ratios of glucose and MMT were dry-mixed by pestle in mortar, pressed into tablets, and pyrolyzed at 1300 °C. Various analytical techniques were used to characterize both original and pyrolyzed samples. Thermogravimetric analysis and elemental analysis were used to confirm the composition of the original samples. Elemental analysis also determined the amount of carbon in pyrolyzed samples. X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) identified phases formed during pyrolysis. Raman microscopy studied the presence of graphite, graphene, and amorphous carbon. Transmission electron microscopy provided an in-depth observation of the morphology, proving that the layers in the pyrolyzed samples matched the d002 distances associated with graphitic carbon as revealed by XRPD analysis. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy confirmed the dominant proportion of sp² carbon (up to 75 %) and revealed a minor proportion of carbon-oxygen bonds (< 15 %). The combined results confirmed that pyrolysis of mechanochemically intercalated MMT yields a material that is similarly conductive to that prepared by pyrolysis of MMT intercalated in water. This is an important step in the process of simplifying the preparation of electrically conductive nanocomposites containing graphite or graphene.

1. Introduction

Graphene has garnered significant attention from the scientific community since its discovery in 2004 by Andre Geim and Konstantin Novoselov through mechanical exfoliation of graphite [1]. Formed from carbon atoms arranged in a single-atom-thick honeycomb lattice [2], graphene is known for its unique properties such as high mechanical strength, high thermal and electrical conductivity, impermeability to gases, large surface area, etc. [3–7]. In addition to a single-atom-thick graphene, other materials based on it are also known, such as few-layer graphene, multi-layer graphene, graphene microsheet, graphene nanoribbon, etc. [2], which form a group of so-called graphene-based materials (GBM; [2]).

GBM are often used as components of nanocomposites, i.e.,

composites in which at least one dimension of at least one component is <100 nm [8]. Such nanocomposites can be prepared by adding commercially available GBM to a selected matrix, e.g., polymers, metals or elastomers [9–12], however, the *in situ* formation of GBM from carbonaceous precursors (SiC [13,14], synthetic polymers and resins [16–24,27–29,32], starch [17], or low molecular weight compounds like sucrose [15,25,26,31], pyrene [32,33], styrene [32,33], ionic liquids [30], or anilinium [34]) has also been widely reported. Common matrices for the *in situ* formation of GBM are clay minerals, usually montmorillonite (MMT) [15,18,19,21–28,30], but also sepiolite [15], saponite [16], laponite [17], talc [20], or halloysite [31].

Pyrolysis of precursors and matrices usually leads to the formation of graphite [15–20,22–31,34] and/or GBM [15,17,22–27,29,34], and the resulting nanocomposites are suggested or directly studied for various

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practical applications (adsorbents [15–17,21], catalysts [16,25,28], reinforcing agents [20], electrodes [27,28], etc.). An important prerequisite for the successful use of the material in practice is the simplicity and low cost of its preparation. To this end, unnecessary steps should be eliminated. The fact that low molecular weight compounds yield graphitic and GBM structures comparable to those prepared from macromolecular compounds is a positive finding, as it shows the possibility of omitting the polymerization step (for more information, the reader is referred to our previous study [34]). Some authors report the use of macromolecular precursors without the need for polymerization, such as natural starch [17] or waste polystyrene and polyethylene terephthalate [20], however, these approaches have some disadvantages. The starch was preheated in water for 2 h to form a gel [17], which lengthens the preparation and brings additional cost. Waste polystyrene and polyethylene terephthalate resulted in graphite, but not GBM [20].

Another simplification that comes to mind when looking for simpler and cheaper preparation is the elimination of the solvent and any solution at all. Common practice is to work with a solution (either during the synthesis of the precursor and/or when mixing it with the matrix), most often with an aqueous solution [15–19,21–25,27,29,31,34] or with solution based on other solvents (e.g., ethanol [28] or benzene [32,33]). However, this wet route requires subsequent filtration, evaporation, drying, etc., which complicates the process and increases its cost. Exceptions can be found in the literature, e.g., microwave-assisted liquefaction (caramelization) of sucrose in the presence of MMT [26]. Although a GBM-containing nanocomposite was obtained [26], the application of microwave radiation brings additional cost. Dry mixing of waste polystyrene or polyethylene terephthalate with a matrix has already been mentioned, as has its result – graphite without GBM [20]. Another exception is the saturation of the matrix with styrene, ethylene, and propylene vapors [32,33]. Although this process is solvent-free, the pyrolysis resulted in disordered carbon with "quasigraphitic crystallites" [32,33].

To the best of our knowledge, a process without macromolecules, without polymerization, without solvent, without preheating (whether for dissolution [17], liquefaction [26], or evaporation [32,33]), without drying, etc., leading to the production of an electrically conductive nanocomposite containing GBM, has not yet been reported. This was the inspiration for our study, which is a continuation of our long-term research focused on nanocomposites of this type [22–24,34]. The first three studies focused on GBM-containing nanocomposites obtained by pyrolysis of polymer/montmorillonite intercalates prepared by the wet route [22–24]. The fourth study aimed to eliminate the polymerization step. GBM-containing nanocomposites were obtained by pyrolysis of low molecular weight compound (anilinium)/montmorillonite intercalates, which were nevertheless still prepared by a wet route [34].

In the present study, we have proceeded to a further simplification by eliminating the solvent: we present the dry mechanochemical intercalation of a montmorillonite with a low molecular weight carbon precursor (glucose). Mixing with a pestle in a mortar is fast, environmentally friendly, cost-effective, and does not require any special equipment. Confirming the feasibility of this dry route would be an important and useful contribution to simplifying the synthesis of electrically conductive GBM-containing nanocomposites.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

D-glucose (GL) anhydrous ($C_6H_{12}O_6$; p.a.) was purchased from mikroCHEM, Slovakia. The ideal amount of C, H, and O in pure GL is 40.0, 6.7, and 50.3 wt.%, respectively. Sodium-rich montmorillonite (MMT) Portaclay® ($(Al_{2.85}Mg_{0.71}Ti_{0.02}Fe_{0.42}^{3+})(Si_8)O_{20}(OH)_4$; layer charge of ~ 0.7 el [24]) was purchased from Ankerpoort NV, Netherlands. Size fraction $< 40 \mu m$ was used. Argon ($>99.9999\%$

purity) was purchased from SIAD Czech, Czech Republic.

2.2. Preparation of samples

Four different MMT:GL mass ratios (1:4, 2:3, 3:2, and 4:1) were dry-mixed with a pestle in a mortar for 10 min. The original (non-pyrolyzed) powder samples MMT_GL prepared this way, denoted as 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL, and 4M_1GL, were pressed without any binder into tablets ($28 \times 28 \times 2$ mm) using the HJC 12 Plus, uni-max table hydraulic press ($p = 25 \cdot 10^3$ kPa; $t = 10$ min).

The pressed tablets were pyrolyzed in the high-temperature tube resistance furnace (CLASIC CZ, spol. s.r.o., Czech Republic) with the internal tube volume of $2.26 \cdot 10^{-3} m^3$ and equipped with a Pt-13 % Rh/Pt thermocouple. Inert atmosphere ($>99.9999\%$ Ar) was maintained under a constant overpressure of $1.06 \cdot 10^5$ Pa. The process included controlled heating and cooling within a temperature range of 25 to 1300 °C at a rate of $5^\circ C \cdot min^{-1}$. The tablets were exposed to the target temperature of 1300 °C for 1 h. The Ar atmosphere in the furnace was exchanged four times during the process: upon reaching a temperature of 900, 1100, 1300 °C, and finally after 1 h at a temperature of 1300 °C (i.e. before the start of cooling). The Ar flow rate during each exchange was $5 dm^3 \cdot min^{-1}$ for 10 min. Pyrolyzed samples were denoted as 1M_4GL(p), 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL(p).

2.3. Characterization methods

Elemental analysis was performed in Elementar vario EL Cube analyser (Elementar, Germany). Each sample was analyzed twice. Accuracy < 0.1 wt.% for each element (C,H,N,S) was ensured by simultaneous analysis of 4-aminobenzenesulfonic acid as a standard.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using STA 409 EP thermogravimeter (Netzsch, Germany) equipped with highly sensitive analytical balances. For the analysis, ~ 20 mg of the sample in an $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ crucible was heated to 1000 °C in a dynamic Ar atmosphere. Heating rate and flow rate were $10^\circ C \cdot min^{-1}$ and $0.1 dm^3 \cdot min^{-1}$, respectively. Mass percentage of GL (w_{GL} ; wt.%) in each sample was calculated from the following equation

$$w_{GL} = 100 \cdot (\Delta m_{MMT_GL} - \Delta m_{MMT}) / (\Delta m_{GL} - \Delta m_{MMT}). \quad (1)$$

where Δm_{MMT_GL} , Δm_{MMT} , and Δm_{GL} is a mass loss (in wt.%) of MMT:GL mixture, pure MMT, and pure GL, respectively. Temperature range of 183–983 °C was used for the calculation.

X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) analysis was performed using a Miniflex600 powder diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan) equipped with a cobalt anode source ($\lambda_{Co,K\alpha} = 1.7889 \text{ \AA}$) and a DTex/Ultra 1D detector. Measurements were carried out in reflection mode with symmetrical Bragg-Brentano geometry. Data were collected over a 2θ range from 5° to 60° with a step size of 0.02° and a scanning speed of $5^\circ \cdot min^{-1}$. The PDXL-2 database (Release 2019) was used to determine the phase composition of the samples.

Molecular modeling was performed in the Materials Studio (MS) modeling environment (Biovia, USA). Montmorillonite (MMT) unit cell ($Al_2Si_4O_{10}(OH)_2$; $a = 5.18 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.97 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.9 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.6^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$ [36]) was expanded into $3a \times 6b \times 1c$ supercell, and its composition $Al_{72}Si_{144}O_{360}(OH)_{72}$ was modified to $(Al_{51}Mg_{13}Fe_3^{3+})(Si_{144})O_{360}(OH)_{72}$ according to the composition of real MMT Portaclay® [24]. Lattice parameters a , b , and γ were fixed. Charges of atoms in the model were calculated using the charge equilibration (QEq) method [37], and the negative layer charge ($x = -13$ el.) was compensated by Na^+ cations. Various numbers of GL molecules and water molecules (having atomic charges calculated using the QEq method) were introduced into the interlayer space together with the cations. The Universal force field [38] was used for parameterization of atoms. Geometry optimization of all MMT models with various interlayer content was performed in MS/Forcite module using Smart algorithm under the

following convergence criteria: $E = 0.001$ kcal/mol, $F = 0.5$ kcal/mol/Å, $d = 0.015$ Å. In optimized models, the basal spacing (d_{001}) values were determined by simulated XRPD performed in MS/Reflex module under the same conditions as the experimental XRPD analysis.

Raman spectra were obtained in the 180-degree backscattering configuration using DXR SmartRaman dispersive Raman spectrometer (ThermoScientific, USA) equipped with 532 nm excitation laser and a CCD detector. Grating, aperture, and exposure time (250 exposures) were 900 lines-mm⁻¹, 50 μm, and 1 s, respectively. Fluorescence was corrected using spectral software OMNIC (v.9.2; Thermo Scientific, USA).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyses were performed using transmission electron microscope JEOL 2010 HC (JEOL Ltd., Japan) equipped with LaB₆ as a source of electrons. Accelerating voltage of 160 kV was used. Distances on the TEM images were measured in ImageJ software [35].

The XPS was performed in Thermo NEXSA G2 instrument with a charge compensation by electrons with 0.5 eV, 100 uA combined with Argon atoms neutralizer. The monochromatic Al X-ray source was set to a spot diameter of 400 μm. The survey spectra were collected at Epass 200 eV (2 scans), and the high-resolution spectra were collected at Epass 20 eV (5 scans) in scanning mode with 0.1 eV step. The full width at half maximum for reference Ag2d5/2 with the setting is < 0.6 eV. Three probes were taken from each sample. The probes were measured independently and the averages and standard deviations were evaluated. Spectra were processed and analyzed in CasaXPS software.

2.4. Determination of electrical conductivity

Pyrolyzed tablets were crushed into fine powder. Each sample was then inserted in a vertical glass tube (internal diameter 3.9 mm) between two copper rod electrodes. The electric current passing through the sample at constant voltage ($U = 1 \pm 0.001$ V; voltage source DC power supply HY 3003 D-2) was recorded for 5 min using measuring card PCI-6221 and processed in original software designed in LabVIEW environment. Scheme of the measuring apparatus is provided in Fig. S1.

The electrical conductivity σ (S·m⁻¹) was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\sigma = (I \cdot d) / (U \cdot S). \quad (2)$$

where I is the average value of the electric current (A), d is the distance between the copper rod electrodes (m), U is the voltage (V), and S is the cross-sectional area of the copper rod electrode (m²).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure and composition of original samples

Elemental analysis of original MMT_GL samples showed carbon and hydrogen contents consistent with the ideal C_{id} and H_{id} values (Table 1).

Table 1

Elemental analysis of original samples. For each sample, two measurements were performed. For comparison, the ideal amounts of C, H, and O (C_{id} , H_{id} , O_{id}) are provided along with their sum showing the ideal GL amount in the sample (Σ). The real GL amounts determined from TG analysis according to Eq. (1) (w_{GL}) are listed in the last column. All values are in wt.%.

Sample	C	H	S	C_{id}	H_{id}	O_{id}	Σ	w_{GL}
1M_4GL_1	32.14	5.71	0.06	32.0	5.3	42.7	80	70.16
1M_4GL_2	32.40	5.70	0.06	32.0	5.3	42.7	80	70.16
2M_3GL_1	25.08	4.63	0.10	24.0	4.0	32.0	60	53.49
2M_3GL_2	24.80	4.55	0.11	24.0	4.0	32.0	60	53.49
3M_2GL_1	16.51	3.37	0.16	16.0	2.7	21.3	40	37.75
3M_2GL_2	16.47	3.33	0.15	16.0	2.7	21.3	40	37.75
4M_1GL_1	8.67	2.24	0.22	8.0	1.3	10.7	20	23.34
4M_1GL_2	8.85	2.24	0.22	8.0	1.3	10.7	20	23.34

The regular increase in sulfur content with increasing MMT content suggests the origin of sulfur in MMT.

TG analysis (Fig. 2) allowed to determine the GL content in original MMT_GL samples according to the Eq. (1): 70.16 wt.%, 53.49 wt.%, 37.75 wt.%, and 23.34 wt.% for 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL, and 4M_1GL, respectively (Table 1). The ideal amount of GL in 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL, and 4M_1GL is 80, 60, 40, and 20 wt.%, respectively (Table 1), and TG-determined values are overall consistent.

XRPD analysis (Fig. 1a) showed that all MMT_GL samples exhibited reflections corresponding to crystalline GL indicating that GL is located not only in the MMT interlayer but also on the MMT surface and between MMT particles. Intensities of the most intensive GL reflection ($\sim 24^\circ 2\theta$) correlate well with the GL amount present in each sample. All nanocomposite samples exhibit increased intensity and shift of the basal reflection to lower 2θ angles compared to pure MMT (Fig. 1b). An increase in the interlayer spacing (~ 2 Å in all nanocomposites) confirms the successful intercalation of GL into the interlayer space of MMT. The arrangement of GL in the MMT interlayer is confirmed by the narrowing of the basal reflection compared to pure MMT (FWHM = 1.32°). The FWHM values increase with decreasing GL content as follows: 0.703°, 0.712°, 0.732°, 1.201° for 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL and 4M_1GL respectively.

Molecular modeling revealed that the d_{001} values of samples 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL, and 4M_1GL ($d_{001} = 13.97$ – 14.16 Å; Fig. 1) correspond to models containing 15 or 16 GL molecules and 10 H₂O molecules in the MMT interlayer space (Fig. S2). These numbers represent 16.5 or 17.4 wt.% GL and ~ 1.1 wt.% H₂O, respectively. According to these results, ~ 24 , ~ 31 , ~ 43 , and ~ 68 % of the total GL amount in 1M_4GL, 2M_3GL, 3M_2GL, and 4M_1GL, respectively, is located in the MMT interlayer space.

3.2. Structure and composition of pyrolyzed samples

Elemental analysis reveals a correlation between the carbon content in the pyrolyzed samples (Table 2) and the initial GL content (Table 1). As the GL content in the original samples increases, the resulting carbon content after pyrolysis also increases (Fig. S3).

Similar behavior was observed for the samples of MMT intercalated with anilinium (MMT_An), where the carbon content in pyrolyzed samples increased with the rising amount of An in the original samples [34]. This similarity (see Fig. S3) shows that different methods of preparing the original samples, i.e. dry mixing of GL with MMT in this study vs. intercalation of An into the MMT in water [34], do not affect the result of the pyrolysis process.

No nitrogen was detected in any of the samples. The increased amount of sulfur compared to the original samples (compare Tables 1 and 2) confirms the origin of sulfur in MMT (see Section 3.1) and suggests a relative increase in MMT content in the pyrolyzed samples due to the mass loss of GL. This is also related to the relative increase in carbon content observed for 1M_4GL(p) (Table 2) which can be explained by the release of oxygen and hydrogen from GL during pyrolysis.

XRPD analysis (Fig. 3a) revealed the formation of an amorphous carbon phase, as evidenced by a broad hump in the range of 20–35° 2θ. In the case of 1M_4GL(p), the d_{001} diffraction line of MMT ($\sim 8^\circ 2\theta$) was preserved after pyrolysis, which may be attributed to the encapsulation of MMT particles by the highly abundant GL in this sample. In all samples, the (002) reflection of graphite appears at $\sim 31^\circ 2\theta$ (Fig. 3a), with an interlayer spacing of $d_{002} = 3.34$ Å [2,39]. As a result of the thermal transformation of the MMT structure, low cristobalite and mullite phases were formed in the 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL (p) samples. These phases have already been observed after the transformation of clay minerals at high temperatures [24,34,40,41]. In the 4M_1GL(p) sample with the originally highest MMT, indialite was also detected, traces of which are also visible in the XRD pattern of 3M_2GL (p) sample (Fig. 3a).

Formation of graphitic carbon during the pyrolysis was confirmed by

Fig. 1. (a) XRPD patterns of original nanocomposites, pure GL (PDF 00-024-1964), and MMT (PDF 00-058-2010, 00-060-0318) with quartz admixture (PDF 01-070-7344). The reflection indices of quartz are denoted by Q. (b) Detail of diffractogram with basal reflections (001) of pure MMT and original MMT_GL nanocomposites.

Fig. 2. TG curves of pure MMT, pure GL, and original MMT_GL nanocomposites.

the presence of both characteristic bands G (graphitic band; $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and D (disorder band; $\sim 1340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in Raman spectra (Fig. 3b). The intensity ratio I_D/I_G , which increases with decreasing carbon content (0.860, 1.127, 1.129, and 1.310 for 1M_4GL(p), 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL(p), respectively), suggests an increasing disorder in the graphitic structure [24,42] with increasing amount of inorganic phases formed from the MMT during pyrolysis. The dependence of I_D/I_G on carbon content in pyrolyzed samples (Fig. S4) is not much different from the MMT_An samples reported in our earlier study [34]. This also proves the very similar behavior of organic molecules in both types of nanocomposites, regardless of the preparation method: dry mixing of GL with

Table 2

Elemental analysis (in wt.%) of pyrolyzed samples. For each sample, two measurements were performed.

Sample	C	H	S
4M_1GL(p)_1	3.07	0.12	0.25
4M_1GL(p)_2	3.09	0.11	0.25
3M_2GL(p)_1	10.27	0.25	0.18
3M_2GL(p)_2	10.22	0.23	0.17
2M_3GL(p)_1	25.91	0.32	0.28
2M_3GL(p)_2	25.82	0.32	0.29
1M_4GL(p)_1	44.50	0.87	0.37
1M_4GL(p)_2	44.72	0.85	0.38

MMT in this study vs. intercalation of An into the MMT in water [34].

The so-called saddle between D and G bands ($\sim 1400\text{--}1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; Fig. 3b) reveals that GL was transformed not only into graphitic but also into amorphous carbon [43]. According to the Raman spectra, the 1M_4GL(p) contains more amorphous carbon compared to other samples (Fig. 3b). The 1M_4GL(p) also shows defects in the graphitic layers, which are manifested by a not very intense but clearly visible band at $\sim 1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [44] (Fig. 3b). These findings correspond to the highest amount of GL in the original mixture. It can be expected that GL without direct contact with MMT (and such GL is the majority in the 1M_4GL(p) sample) is not transformed to graphitic carbon during pyrolysis as successfully as GL on the surface of MMT (serving as a solid matrix). At the same time, however, the high GL content allows the entire available surface of MMT to be covered with GL, which in this close contact transforms into a relatively well-ordered graphitic structure (see the highest intensity of the G band in the spectrum of the 1M_4GL(p) sample in Fig. 3b).

With decreasing GL content and increasing MMT content, the proportion of GL without contact with MMT decreases, and therefore the

Fig. 3. (a) XRPD patterns of pyrolyzed samples. C – low cristobalite (PDF 01-076-0941), G – graphite (PDF 00-56-0159), I – indialite (PDF 01-070-6381), M – mullite (PDF 01-079-1457). (b) Raman spectra of pyrolyzed samples.

content of amorphous carbon also decreases (see the lower saddles in the spectra of 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL(p) samples in Fig. 3b). Although the disorder of the formed graphitic structures is higher in these samples (see $I_D > I_G$ in Fig. 3b), the defects in the layers are reduced, as indicated by the absence of the band at $\sim 1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of these samples (Fig. 3b).

The sharp band at $\sim 2325 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ present in all Raman spectra does not originate from the samples, but from atmospheric nitrogen [45]. The spectra of 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL(p) contain an overtone band (2D; $\sim 2680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) whose intensity relative to the G band, i.e. I_{2D}/I_G , allows determining the presence of graphene structures [46,47]: 0.31, 0.34, and 0.15 for 2M_3GL(p), 3M_2GL(p), and 4M_1GL(p), respectively. The presented values indicate that monolayer graphene cannot be expected in the pyrolyzed samples (the I_{2D}/I_G ratio would have to be > 1 [46,47]). However, the multi-layer graphene (i.e. having 10 or fewer layers [2,48]) is not ruled out, and TEM analysis was used to confirm or refute its presence.

3.3. Morphology of pyrolyzed samples

TEM analysis (Fig. 4) revealed carbon structures in all pyrolyzed samples. However, noticeable differences can be observed. In the 1M_4GL(p) sample, carbon was found in the form of clusters without visible regular arrangement (Fig. 4a). The TEM analysis thus agrees with the largest amount of amorphous carbon and defects in layers detected by Raman spectroscopy in the 1M_4GL(p) (Fig. 3b). The cause of the disorder is probably the large excess of GL compared to MMT, i.e. most of the GL was transformed during pyrolysis without contact with MMT. The carbon structure observed in the 1M_4GL(p) (Fig. 4a) resembles frayed veils and is similar to the carbon obtained by pyrolysis of e.g. ionic liquids with MMT [30]. The used mass ratio IL:MMT = 2:1 [30] lies between the mass ratios used for the preparation of the 1M_4GL(p) (GL:MMT = 4:1) and 2M_3GL(p) (GL:MMT = 3:2) samples. This supports the hypothesis that the cause is an excess of organic precursor.

The threshold for the formation of these structures as the dominant form must lie above the mass ratio of 3:2, because in samples 2M_3GL(p) (Fig. 4b) and 3M_2GL(p) (Fig. 4c) a different carbon structure dominates. It resembles bent "stalks", often twisted into "rings". These sometimes surround silicate particles as "shells" (see the white horizontal arrows in Fig. 4b, c). However, they are mostly found separately as "empty shells", which can be explained by their falling off from the surface of the particles on which they originally formed. More TEM images are provided in Fig. S5. An example of visual distinction between carbon and silicate phases is shown in Fig. S6. The same structures as in Fig. 4b,c have already been observed in previous studies focused on the preparation of graphite/graphene-based nanocomposites by pyrolysis of various organic precursors with MMT (e.g. anilinium:MMT with mass ratios from 1:2 to 1:1 [34] or polypyrrole:MMT with 1:1 mass ratio [24]). It seems that a lower precursor:matrix mass ratio is favorable for the formation of these structures. The thickness of most of the "shells" is less than $\sim 25 \text{ nm}$ (Figs. 4b,c and S5; see also Fig. 5) and their presence correlates with the presence of distinct 2D bands in the Raman spectra of 2M_3GL(p) and 3M_2GL(p) (Fig. 3b).

In the 3M_2GL(p) sample, in which MMT already starts to dominate over GL, thicker "shells" can also be observed (see the white vertical arrow in Fig. 4c). These are similar to those found in sample 4M_1GL(p) (Fig. 4d), in which MMT fully dominates (GL:MMT = 1:4). TEM analysis of the 4M_1GL(p) revealed predominantly silicate particles with no carbon (Fig. S7). Carbon was found quite exceptionally and in the form of thick layers (Fig. 4d). This can be explained by the presence of small, isolated clusters of GL, which are only sporadically located between MMT particles. A given GL cluster probably adheres to the nearest MMT particle, on whose surface it is all transformed during pyrolysis, resulting in the formation of a unique thick "shell" while the other silicate particles remain without carbon (Fig. S6).

In the TEM images with a larger scale, the graphitic layers are clearly visible (Fig. 5). Their clarity allows to determine the number of layers and to calculate the interlayer distance d_{002} (Table 3). The specific

Fig. 4. TEM images of pyrolyzed samples a) 1M_4GL (p), b) 2M_3GL(p), c) 3M_2GL(p), and d) 4M_1GL (p). White horizontal arrows (b,c) point to thin "shells" on the silicate particles. White vertical arrows (c,d) points to thicker "shells".

Fig. 5. TEM images of pyrolyzed samples a) 2M_3GL(p) and b) 3M_2GL(p). The locations of the interlayer distance measurements are marked with white lines and numbered (see Table 3).

locations where the layers were counted are marked on the TEM images (Fig. 5). The average value $d_{002} = 0.335 \pm 0.002$ nm corresponds to the interlayer spacing in graphite [2,39,49]. The number of layers < 10 in

all but one measurement (Table 3) indicates the presence of multi-layer graphene [2,48].

Table 3

Interlayer distance values (d_{002}) of graphitic carbon obtained from TEM images (Fig. 5) by dividing the length of the line (L) by the number of layers (N) crossing the line. Measurement numbers (No.) and references to TEM images (Fig.) are also provided.

d_{002} (nm)	L (nm)	N (-)	No.	Fig.
0.332	1.326	4	1	5a
0.335	2.342	7	2	5a
0.337	3.703	11	3	5a
0.337	2.359	7	4	5a
0.334	2.002	6	1	5b
0.334	2.338	7	2	5b
0.337	3.033	9	3	5b

3.4. Electrical conductivity of pyrolyzed samples

Structural and spectroscopic analyses confirmed the presence of a graphitic carbon phase in the prepared nanocomposites, indicating their potential for electrical conductivity. This assumption was subsequently confirmed by direct conductivity measurements (Table 4).

The electrical conductivity of pyrolyzed samples reaches a maximum at ~26 wt.% carbon, i.e. for 2M_3GL(p) sample (Fig. 6a). Very similar trend was observed for pyrolyzed MMT_An samples in our earlier study [34], where electrical conductivity reached a maximum at ~20 wt.% carbon (Fig. 6a), which was the largest amount of carbon in the pyrolyzed MMT_An samples. However, data for MMT_GL samples show that when the amount of carbon exceeds ~26 wt.%, the conductivity decreases (Fig. 6a). This decrease, which occurs in the case of 1M_4GL(p) sample, is also evident in the dependence of conductivity on I_D/I_G ratio (Fig. 6b). While for conductivity of samples with carbon content up to ~26 wt.%, a significant similarity to the pyrolyzed MMT_An samples from our earlier study [34] can again be observed, the overall trend is disrupted by the 1M_4GL(p) sample (Fig. 6b). Since its conductivity is not as high as one would expect considering the I_D/I_G value, the reason for the reduced value must therefore be sought elsewhere. The likely cause seems to be not only an increased amount of amorphous carbon, but above all the high level of defects in graphitic layers, as shown by Raman spectrum of this sample (see Fig. 3b). The negligible conductivity of 4M_1GL(p) sample (Table 6) can be explained by the very low carbon content (~3 wt.%; Table 2) and its rare occurrence among pure silicate particles, as revealed by TEM analysis (see Section 3.3).

3.5. On carbon in electrically conductive samples

To obtain a more detailed picture of carbon in conductive samples, XPS analysis was also performed. Due to the almost zero conductivity of sample 4M_1GL(p) (Table 4), only samples 3M_2GL(p), 2M_3GL(p), and 1M_4GL(p) were analyzed (Fig. S8). The composition determined by XPS supported the findings obtained from previous analyses. An increase in carbon content with increasing amount of GL in the original mixture and a decrease in the content of elements associated with MMT was found (Table S1). Subsequently, attention was focused on carbon.

The sp^2 and sp^3 hybridized states of carbon can be distinguished based on the shape of the C KLL Auger peaks in the XPS spectra. Because literature emphasizes the necessary quality of the data, i.e., that the derivatives without smoothing may be too noisy to be useful [50,51],

smoothing by SG Linear (21) before SG Quadratic (5) differentiation in CasaXPS software was used. The shape of the derivatives is similar for all samples (Fig. 7). The bold dashed lines in Fig. 7 indicate a D-parameter of ~22 eV characteristic of sp^2 carbon (the D-parameter value for sp^2 carbon ranges from 20 to 24 eV [50]). Since a sp^3 carbon is indicated by a D-parameter in the range of ~13–15 eV [50,51], both states are well distinguishable. The peak for the D-parameter of sp^3 carbon can be expected at ~262 eV (thin dashed line in Fig. 7). In the case of typical sp^2 carbon, a valley is commonly observed at this position, but is absent here. This suggests the presence of some sp^3 carbon in the samples.

The high-resolution C1s spectra (Fig. 8) of all three samples show a single-peak character and their FWHM values are comparable (0.9 ± 0.1 for both 3M_2GL(p) and 1M_4GL(p), 0.8 ± 0.1 for 2M_3GL(p)). In addition to the dominant sp^2 state, a sp^3 state is also expected, and due to the presence of oxygen in GL, carbon-oxygen bonds are not excluded. While the shift of the sp^3 vs. the sp^2 component should be in the range of 0.7–1.2 eV of binding energy [50,51], in the case of carbon-oxygen bonds the typical shift is ~1.5 eV or more [52].

The components used for the fitting including the corresponding binding energy (eV) and shift (eV) values [52,53] can be found in Table 5 and the resulting average quantities (in %) of different bond types are provided in Table 6. It should be noted that the components corresponding to carbon-oxygen bonds do not represent the exact chemical composition, but show probable bond structures common to similar binding energies. However, this is not an obstacle because these bonds are minor (< 15 %; Table 6) and sp^2 carbon clearly dominates in the samples. When standard deviations are taken into account, the samples do not show any significant differences. The exception is sp^2 carbon, the amount of which in 2M_3GL(p) and 1M_4GL(p) is significantly higher compared to the amount of sp^2 carbon in 3M_2GL(p) (Table 6). This difference agrees with the higher conductivity of sample 2M_3GL(p) compared to 3M_2GL(p) (Table 4). However, the similarity of the amount of sp^2 carbon in 2M_3GL(p) and 1M_4GL(p) (see Table 6) excludes a connection with a decrease in the conductivity of the latter (Table 4). This fact suggests that the conductivity of sample 1M_4GL(p), lower than 2M_3GL(p) and almost the same as 3M_2GL(p) (see Table 4), is not due to the proportion of different types of bonds in the carbon formed from GL during pyrolysis. The most likely cause is the high level of defects caused by the strong excess of GL over MMT, as discussed in Sections 3.3 and 3.4.

4. Conclusions

The dry mechanochemical intercalation of GL into MMT, followed by pyrolysis at 1300 °C in Ar atmosphere, proved to be an effective water-free method to prepare conductive carbon-silicate nanocomposites. Four different mass ratios MMT:GL (4:1, 3:2, 2:3, 1:4) were studied. Depending on the original GL content, the amount of carbon in the pyrolyzed samples increased (according to elemental and TG analyses) as did the I_D/I_G ratio determined by Raman spectroscopy. TEM analysis showed multi-layer graphene structures with an interlayer spacing of ~0.335 nm. XPS analysis showed that the structure of the carbon formed during pyrolysis is dominated by sp^2 carbon (up to 75 %) over sp^3 carbon. The presence of carbon -oxygen bonds was detected, but only in small amounts (< 15 %). Raman spectroscopy revealed that the pyrolyzed sample 1M_4GL(p) with the highest original amount of GL exhibits the largest amorphous carbon content and the highest level of defects in the graphitic layers. This fact was reflected in the electrical conductivity measurements. The highest conductivity values (~36 S·m⁻¹) were not found for the 1M_4GL(p), but for the 2M_3GL(p) with the second lowest I_D/I_G ratio and significantly lower amorphous carbon content. The interdependencies of GL content in original samples, carbon content in pyrolyzed samples, I_D/I_G ratio, and electrical conductivity are very similar to those found in our previous study [34] dealing with conductive nanocomposites prepared from An intercalated into MMT in aqueous environment. The comparisons show the similarity of the

Table 4

Electrical conductivities σ of pyrolyzed samples (according to Eq. (2)).

sample	σ (S·m ⁻¹)
4M_1GL(p)	0.04±0.02
3M_2GL(p)	11.67±3.72
2M_3GL(p)	36.01±8.41
1M_4GL(p)	10.34±1.78

Fig. 6. (a) Dependence of electrical conductivity σ (Table 4) on amount of carbon (Table 1) for pyrolyzed samples MMT_GL (red diamonds; this study) and MMT_An (black squares; [34]). (b) Dependence of electrical conductivity σ (Table 4) on ID/IG ratio for pyrolyzed samples MMT_GL (red diamonds; this study) and MMT_An (black squares; [34]).

Fig. 7. The C KLL derivatives on all three probes from 3M_2GL(p), 2M_3GL(p), and 1M_4GL(p). The vertical bold dashed lines indicate a D-parameter of ~ 22 eV characteristic of sp^2 carbon. The vertical thin dashed lines indicate a peak for the D-parameter of sp^3 carbon.

behavior of organic molecules in both types of nanocomposites regardless of the preparation method. This is the main result of the present study. Electrically conductive GBM-silicate nanocomposites do not need to be prepared in solution. The use of a solvent and the subsequent filtration and drying are not necessary steps. A simple mechanochemical intercalation performed by dry mixing the organic precursor and clay is sufficient. This environmentally friendly solvent-free method offers a sustainable route to prepare electrically conductive GBM-silicate nanocomposites.

Data availability

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19091378>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Markéta Davidová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Zuzana Pěgřimočová:** Validation, Investigation. **Silvie Vallová:** Validation, Investigation. **Lenka Řeháčková:** Validation, Investigation. **Martin Kormunda:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Lenka Kulhánková:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Table 5

Components used to fit C1s peaks including the corresponding binding energy (BE; eV) and shift from sp^2 (in eV).

component	BE	shift
sp^2	284.5	0.0
sp^3	285.4	+0.9
$\pi-\pi^*$	289.2	+4.7
C-O	286.0	+1.5
C-Ox	287.0	+2.5
C=O	287.7	+3.2

Fig. 8. The high-resolution C1s peaks of (a) 3M_2GL(p), (b) 2M_3GL(p), and (c) 1M_4GL(p).

Table 6

Average quantities (in %) for different bond types, as obtained from the high-resolution C1s peaks. Three measurements were performed for each sample.

	sp ²	sp ³	π-π*	C-O	C-Ox	C=O
3M_2GL	68.7 ± 2.1	8.3 ± 2.4	8.6 ± 0.4	9.9 ± 0.6	3.9 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.3
2M_3GL	75.8 ± 2.9	5.5 ± 2.9	7.0 ± 1.9	8.0 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.1
1M_4GL	74.2 ± 1.6	4.0 ± 1.2	9.3 ± 0.8	8.8 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.3

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.cartre.2026.100635](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cartre.2026.100635).

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